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Microwave Optimization of the Process for Obtaining Activated Carbon from Agricultural Waste

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Abstract:

Carbons activated from lignocellulosic residues by pyrolysis and chemical activation by microwaves and evaluating adsorbent capacity with methylene blue were objectives of the work. Optimum pyrolysis conditions: 400 °C, 30 min, 2 g of precursor, N₂ flow of 150 cm³N₂/min and heating rate of 20 °C/min, yields of 33% and %C of 44-68%. Carbons with anionic surface charges, megaporous structures and less active surfaces for adsorption. Optimum conditions for chemical activation by microwaves: 200 W, 4 min, 60% H₃PO₄ and 200 cm³N₂/min, yields 72-96%, with %C 61-68%. Carbons with larger active surfaces, highly developed mesoporous structures, and a greater number of active sites. Chemisorption, limiting step of the process. Microwave radiation produced specific effects on the surface chemistry, increased C/O ratio, decreased functional groups with acidic oxygen, giving basic activated carbons, effective for methylene blue adsorption

Keywords: optimization, activated carbons, *Agave salmiana*, isotherms, methylene blue

1 Introduction

Microwave energy has a low energy content in its photons (0.03 kcal/mol), which, when compared with the energy of chemical bonds, which ranges from 20 to 80 kcal/mol, is considered relatively low. Consequently, microwaves could not directly affect molecular structure. Therefore, the effect of the excitation of the molecules by microwaves is purely an increase in kinetic energy as mentioned above. Microwaves do not contain enough energy to cause chemical changes in compounds by ionization and are considered non-ionizing radiation [1].

To achieve the effect of microwaves, they must be coupled directly with the molecules of the substance being exposed, thus leading to a rapid increase in temperature. The result of this is an instantaneous heating of any material that exhibits ionic conduction or bipolar rotation, which are the two fundamental mechanisms for the transfer of microwave energy to matter. The bipolar rotation refers to an interaction in which the polar molecules or species try to align themselves with the changing speed of said electric field, the movement and friction between the molecules originate the transfer of energy that is converted into heat.

Coupling ability is related to the polarity of the molecules and their alignment ability. The second way to transfer this energy is by ionic conduction, in which, if there are ionic species or free ions present in the substance, the electric field will generate ionic movement when the molecules try to orient themselves with the field, thus causing rapid heating. This way of transferring energy offers a marked advantage over conventional heating, it should be mentioned that thermal conductivity is not absolutely necessary for microwave heating because this is a volumetric type of process. It can be considered that microwaves cause dielectric heating on compounds with a dipole moment other than zero [1].

In the microwave method, microwave irradiation interacts directly with the particles within the dielectric material through electromagnetic waves, changing the electromagnetic energy in heat transfer to the interior of the materials, resulting in rapid volumetric heating [2]. In this way, the microwave radiation method is both internal and volumetric, where the huge thermal gradient from the interior of the sample to the surface allows microwave-induced reactions to proceed more quickly and efficiently at a lower temperature, providing shorter processing time and lower power consumption.

Under these conditions, the thermal gradient gradually decreases from the center to the surface of the sample due to higher temperatures inside than at the surface of the sample. Due to this temperature gradient, low molecular weight components are easily released to form more pores in the material [2].

Microwave heating is an alternative that allows solving the problems of the thermal gradient and the high cost of preparing activated carbons. In this regard, microwave radiation offers several advantages over conventional heating methods. Table 1 shows a comparison between conventional and microwave heating methods.

Table 1. Comparison between conventional and microwave heating in the production of activated carbons [3].

Parameter	Conventional heating	Microwave heating	Parameter	Conventional heating	Microwave heating
Treatment time	The thermal process can take several hours, even up to a week to reach the desired level of activation, so the process entails additional processing costs.	Treatment time can be considerably reduced, which in many cases represents a reduction in energy consumption as well.	Treatment time	The thermal process can take several hours, even up to a week to reach the desired level of activation, so the process entails additional processing costs.	Treatment time can be considerably reduced, which in many cases represents a reduction in energy consumption as well.
Heating process	• Heating of the surface.		Heating process	• Heating of the surface.	

Dielectric heating is heating through electromagnetic radiation of a wavelength between 0.001 and 1 nm (corresponding to frequencies between 300 and 0.3 GHz), that is, radio waves and microwaves. The interaction of the charged particles of certain materials with the electric field that is part of the electromagnetic radiation causes these materials to heat up. For example, in the case of polar molecules, such as water, the electric field of microwaves causes both the permanent and induced dipoles to rotate when trying to align themselves with the oscillating field, if microwaves at the frequency of 2.45 GHz are being used, the molecule would rotate 2450 million times per second following the electric field. This molecular

movement generates friction between the rotating molecules and energy is dissipated in the form of heat (Dipolar Polarization). In the case of solid dielectric materials with charged particles that have freedom of movement in a delimited region of the material, such as π electrons in coals, the microwaves induce a current in phase with the electromagnetic field in the material. As electrons find resistance to free movement through the material, a certain amount of energy will dissipate in the form of heat (Maxwell-Wagner polarization) [4]. In addition to this, the interaction between inorganic materials and microwaves is normally very weak. Homopolar liquids do not interact with microwaves because they do not have a dipole moment. The interaction between polar liquids and microwaves is particularly strong [1].

Materials that interact with microwaves to generate heat are called microwave absorbers. The ability of a material to heat up in the presence of a microwave field is defined by its tangent of dielectric losses: $\tan \delta = \epsilon''/\epsilon'$ [4]. This tangent is the relationship between the dissipative and capacitive behavior of materials. The value of $\tan \delta$ is easily related to the heating capacity of the materials, the higher the better, while materials with a low loss factor behave as reflective or transparent materials [1]. The immediate application is that when a reaction is carried out, heating will be faster in materials with high loss tangents than in non-absorbent materials.

The dielectric loss tangent is composed of two parameters, the dielectric constant (or real permittivity), ϵ' , and the dielectric loss factor (or imaginary permittivity), ϵ'' ; that is, $\epsilon = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$, where ϵ would be the complex permittivity. The dielectric constant (ϵ') determines how much of the incident energy is reflected and how much absorbed, while the dielectric loss factor (ϵ'') measures the dissipation, in the form of heat, of electrical energy inside the material. Thus, while some materials have a low dielectric loss factor (ϵ'') to allow dielectric heating (transparent to microwaves), other materials, such as some inorganic oxides and most carbon materials, are excellent absorbers of microwave. On the other hand, materials that are electrically conductive reflect microwaves. Thus, graphite and heavily graphitized coals can reflect a significant fraction of microwave radiation [4].

Among the various types of materials, carbon materials are very good microwave absorbers. This characteristic allows transforming carbonaceous materials by microwave heating, giving rise to new carbonaceous materials with modified properties [2, 4]. The high capacity of carbon materials to absorb microwave energy and convert it into heat is illustrated in Table 2, where the tangents of dielectric losses of some of them are shown. As can be seen, the dielectric loss tangents of most coals, except coal, are greater than that of water (0.118 to 2.45 GHz and 298 K) [4]. Based on the loss tangent, the compounds can be classified into three groups of microwaves absorbing materials: high level $\tan > 0.5$, medium level ($0.1 < \tan < 0.5$) and low-level $\tan < 0.1$ [1]. Activated carbons are in the medium and high level as microwave absorbers.

Table 2. Tangent of dielectric losses of different carbon materials at a frequency of 2.45 GHz and a temperature of 298 K [4].

Carbon material	$\tan \delta = \epsilon''/\epsilon'$
Coal	0.02-0.08
Carbon sponges	0.05-0.20
Charcoal	0.11-0.29
Lampblack	0.35-0.83
Activated carbon	0.22-2.95
Carbon nanotube	0.25-1.14
SiC Nanofibers	0.58-1.00

Tables 3 and 4 show the surfaces developed in activated carbons by the microwave activation method with chemical and physical activation, respectively. It is observed that the surfaces obtained with the conventional activation methods are remarkably improved, reaching maximum surfaces of 2557 m^2/g for the chemical activation of tobacco stems with K_2CO_3 and of 2288 m^2/g for the physical activation of coconut shell with CO_2 . In the latter there is a considerable increase in the developed area.

Table 3. Activated carbons produced by the microwave method under optimal conditions with chemical activation [2].

Precursor	Activation agent	SBET ^a (m ² /g)
Pineapple peel	KOH	1006
	K ₂ CO ₃	680
Rice husk	KOH	752
	K ₂ CO ₃	1165
Cotton stalks	KOH	729
	K ₂ CO ₃	621
Orange peels	K ₂ CO ₃	1104
Sunflower Seed Waste	K ₂ CO ₃	1411
Tobacco stems	K ₂ CO ₃	2557
Pistachio shells	KOH	700
Bamboo	H ₃ PO ₄	1432
Lotus stems	H ₃ PO ₄	1434
Cotton stalks	H ₃ PO ₄	652
Tea waste	H ₃ PO ₄	1157
Cotton stalks	ZnCl ₂	794
Pinewood	ZnCl ₂	1459
Industrial waste lignin	ZnCl ₂	1172
Grapefruit peel	NaOH	1355

^aSBET = BET surface areal**Table 4.** Activated carbons produced by the microwave method under optimal conditions with physical activation [2].

Precursor	Activation agent	SBET ^a (m ² /g)
Coconut shell	Steam	2079
	CO ₂	2288
	Mixed	2194
Jatropha husk	Steam	1350
	CO ₂	1284
Oil palm bones	CO ₂	412
Coconut shell	Steam	891

In addition to the above, the literature indicates that physical activation requires higher microwave power levels and longer radiation time than chemical activation, as observed in Tables 5 and 6 [2]. Likewise, Table 7 compiles the physical characteristics of activated carbons obtained by the microwave-assisted chemical activation method from various agricultural residues.

Based on the various studies carried out, the literature establishes the range of 750-3000 W, as the optimal microwave power to produce activated carbons by physical activation, while for chemical activation this range is between 200 and 900 W. In the same vein, it is also added that the optimal range of microwave radiation time for physical activation is from 19 to 210 minutes and for chemical activation it is from 30 seconds to 30 minutes.

Table 5. Activated carbons produced by the microwave method under optimal conditions with physical activation [2].

Precursor	Activation agent	Microwave power (W)	Radiation time (min)
Jatropha husk	Steam	3000	19
	CO ₂	3000	30
Coconut shell	Steam	3000	75
	CO ₂	3000	210
	Mixed	3000	75
Oil palm bones	CO ₂	750	60

Table 6. Activated carbons produced by the microwave method under optimal conditions with chemical activation [2].

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Precursor	Activation agent	Microwave power (W)	Radiation time (min)
Pineapple peel	KOH	600	6
Rice husk	K ₂ CO ₃	600	7
	KOH		
Cotton stalks	KOH	660	10
	K ₂ CO ₃		
Orange peels	K ₂ CO ₃	600	6
Sunflower Seed Waste	K ₂ CO ₃	600	8
Tobacco stems	K ₂ CO ₃	700	30
Pistachio shells	KOH	700	7
Oil palm residues	KOH	360	15
Fruit waste	KOH	600	7
Oil palm fibers	KOH	360	5
Cotton stalks	H ₃ PO ₄	400	8
Lotus stems	H ₃ PO ₄	700	15
Grapefruit peel	NaOH	500	5
Cotton stalks	ZnCl ₂	560	9
Pinewood	ZnCl ₂	700	10

Materials and Methods

2.1. Microwave-assisted chemical activation with H₃PO₄

Samples of 2 g of each study precursor with particle sizes between 1.5 and 0.250 mm, were impregnated with 4 mL of phosphoric acid solution (constant ratio 1: 2 masses of carbon / volume of phosphoric acid) in predetermined concentrations. The samples were soaked in a desiccator for 24 h. After the impregnation time, the samples were placed in a modified industrial multimodal microwave (1800 W, 2450 MHz) for chemical activation. Microwave power, radiation time, phosphoric acid concentration and nitrogen flow rate were considered as control factors. After the process, the activated carbons obtained were thermally equilibrated with room temperature in a desiccator and subsequently washed with hot distilled water (70 ° C) until the pH of the solution was in the range of 6-7. Finally, the activated carbons were dried in an oven at 110 ° C for 24 h and stored for their characterization and later use.

For the microwave-assisted chemical activation process, four control factors named as concentration of the activating agent (Factor A), radiation time (Factor B), microwave power (Factor C) and nitrogen flow rate (Factor C) were defined (Factor D) each evaluated at three levels as shown in Table 8; The precursor evaluated at three levels was considered as noise factor.

Table 7. Summary of yields and physical properties of activated carbons produced under optimal conditions with chemical activation with microwave.

Precursor	Activation agent	Microwave power (W)	Radiation time (min)	SBET ^a (m ² /g)	VT ^b (cm ³ /g)	V _μ ^c (cm ³ /g)	Reference
Bamboo	H ₃ PO ₄	350	20	1432	0.696	0.503	[5]
Peanut shell	H ₃ PO ₄	500	10	953	0.881	0.278	[6]
Wood	H ₃ PO ₄	700	15	519	0.260	0.190	[7]
Oil palm	KOH	360	15	807	0.450	-	[8]
Macadamia nut endocarp	ZnCl ₂	720	20	598	0.300	0.277	[9]
Palm leaves	ZnCl ₂	1050	15	1195	0.650	0.630	[10]
Albizia lebeck	KOH	620	8	1825	-	0.645	[11]
Mangosteen peel	K ₂ CO ₃	600	5	1099	0.611	0.334	[12]
Jackfruit shell	NaOH	600	7	1287	0.764	0.356	[12]
Coconut shell	KOH	600	6	1356	0.780	0.392	[12]
Lotus stems	H ₃ PO ₄	700	15	1220	1.191	0.2858	[13]
Oil palm fibers	NaOH	360	5	708	0.3805	-	[8]

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Pumpkin seed husk	KOH	600	12	734	0.370	0.301	[14]
Orange peel	K ₂ CO ₃	600	6	1104	0.615	0.247	[12]
Wood sawdust	K ₂ CO ₃	600	6	1496	0.864	0.470	[12]
Sunflower seeds	K ₂ CO ₃	600	8	1411	0.836	-	[8]
Oil palm fibers	KOH	600	6	1223	0.72	0.42	[12]
Tea waste	H ₃ PO ₄	900	.5	1417	1.1866	0.2946	[15]
Rambutan peel	KOH	600	12	972	0.642	0.162	[16]
Palm leaves	ZnCl ₂	1200	15	1253	0.83	-	[2]

2.2. Experimental design

The production of activated carbon from biomass requires the consideration of several factors. Therefore, it is essential to adopt an experimental statistical design that allows making various experimental setups and reducing the number of experiments efficiently [17]. In this sense, the Taguchi methodology is a valuable tool and has been implemented by various researchers in various optimization processes.

Table 8. Experimental design matrix for microwave-assisted chemical activation with H₃PO₄.

Level	Control factors				Noise factor		
	A [H ₃ PO ₄] (%)	B Time (min)	C Power (W)	D Flow of N ₂ (cm ³ /min)	R1	R2	R3
1	30	30	200	100	Barley husk	Corn cobs	Agave leaves
2	60	60	400	150			
3	85	90	600	200			

The Taguchi design is an orthogonal arrangement method that significantly reduces the number of experimental setups and provides an independent assessment of factors through a small number of trials [18]. According to the literature, this experimental design uses orthogonal matrices to organize the parameters that affect the process and the level at which they must be varied. In this way, instead of having to test all possible combinations, the Taguchi method tests pairs of combinations to determine which factors most affect product quality with a minimum of experimentation [17].

Unlike conventional methods that use only the mean value of response to determine the optimal level without showing the variability of the data set, the Taguchi method takes into account both the mean value and the variance. In this sense, [17] mention that an important aspect that must be considered in optimization is the signal/noise ratio (S/N), which is an analytical tool used to determine the best levels which contribute to the optimal response value.

In this work, the Taguchi orthogonal matrix design was implemented as a systematic method to obtain the optimal conditions for obtaining activated carbon from the precursors and activation methods mentioned in previous paragraphs. This design was used with the objective of maximizing carbon yields in all activation methods by analyzing the effect of the parameters of each process.

An L₉ orthogonal arrangement was used with four operational parameters that were called control factors, with three levels for each one, as shown in the experimental design matrix of each activation method.

In addition to the above, in the Taguchi method there are three main types of signal-to-noise ratio, which are "lower better", "nominal better" and "higher better." In this work, the signal-to-noise ratio "higher activated carbon yield better" was used since the objective in each activation method is to obtain the highest possible response value.

The noise factor in this study is the raw material defined equally at three levels. In this sense, the barley husk was considered as noise factor 1 (R1), corn cobs as noise factor 2 (R2) and agave leaves as noise factor 3 (R3). Table 9 shows the L₉ orthogonal design matrix with the mentioned noise factors. It is important to mention that the design matrix shown was provided by ANTM 2.5, which is a statistical software that incorporates the Taguchi L₉ orthogonal design method.

A regular analysis of the results and the calculation of the ANOVA with the indicated software was carried out to find the optimal combination of levels by variables that correspond to the optimal results of the defined response. Once the optimal operating conditions were found, confirmatory experiments were carried out for the optimization of the yields. Finally, by comparing the physical and chemical characteristics of each carbonaceous material, the best activated carbon was defined.

Table 9. $L_9(3)^4$ experimental design matrix.

Exp.	Control factors				Noise factor		
	A	B	C	D	R1	R2	R3
1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3
2	2	2	2	3	4	5	6
3	3	3	3	2	7	8	9
4	1	2	2	3	10	11	12
5	2	3	1	2	13	14	15
6	3	1	3	1	16	17	18
7	1	3	3	3	19	20	21
8	2	1	1	2	22	23	24
9	3	2	2	1	25	26	27

2.3. Characterization of activated carbons

The optimal activated carbons were characterized physically and chemically by the following determinations and analysis techniques.

- Determination of moisture content according to the ASTM D3173 (1996) method [19].
- Ashes according to the ASTM D3174 (2000) method [20].
- Volatile matter using the ASTM D3175 (1997) method [21].
- Fixed carbon using the ASTM D3172 (1997) method [22].
- Elemental analysis of C, H and N using a Perkin Elmer model 2400 PECHNSO analyzer, using He as entrainment gas, O₂ as combustion gas and N₂ as pneumatic gas.
- Infrared spectroscopy in tablets with KBr in an FTIR equipment from Perkin Elmer (Spectrum one). The spectrum was performed in the region from 370 to 4000 cm⁻¹, with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and 10 scans.
- Thermogravimetric (TGA) and derivative (DTGA) analysis in an analyzer from METTLER-TOLEDO, model TGA/SDTGA-851, in aluminum crucibles and with a sweep of 25 °C to 600 °C at a speed of 10 °C min⁻¹.
- X-ray powder diffraction on a Bruker D2 Phaser 2nd Gen equipment for 2θ values from 5° to 70° using CuKα radiation with a wavelength of 1.54184 Å and a Lynxeye detector (ID mode).
- Scanning electron microscopy using a JEOL model JSM 6300 scanning electron microscope, operating at 10 kV. For observation, particles of the precursors and carbons were placed on a carbon ribbon and covered with gold.
- Z potential in a Zetasizer nanoseries equipment from Malvern.

2.4. Evaluation of adsorbent capacity

2.4.1. Kinetic experiments

To determine the optimal contact time, 0.2 g samples of activated carbon with a particle size of 1.5-0.250 mm were added to 50 mL of a methylene blue solution with an initial concentration of 50 mg/L. contained in an Erlenmeyer flask at pH = 8 and T = 22 °C. The chemical structure of methylene blue (MB) in a basic medium shows its cationic character. The mixture was stirred at 200 rpm and samples were taken at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 min, the absorbance being measured in a spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer instruments Lamda 40 UV/VIS spectrometer) at a wavelength of 664 nm [23-24]. This

procedure was performed in triplicate for each adsorbent. To determine the final concentration of methylene blue, a calibration curve was made, obtaining the equation of the line with an R^2 of 0.9992.

The efficiency of methylene blue adsorption (% E) from the batch experiments was calculated using Equation (1):

$$\%E = \left[\frac{(C_0 - C_t)}{C_0} \right] * 100 \quad \text{Ec. (1)}$$

Where C_0 is the initial concentration of MB (mg/L), and C_t is the concentration of MB (mg/L) at contact time t (min).

The amount of MB adsorbed or adsorption capacity (q_t , mg/L) at time t (min) for each experiment was calculated using Equation (2):

$$q_t = [(C_0 - C_t)/W] * V \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Where q_t is the amount of MB adsorbed (mg/L) on the activated carbon at time t (min), C_0 and C_t are the same as the previous ones, V is the experimental volume of the solution (L) and W is the weight of activated carbon used (g) [23].

2.4.2. Adsorption tests

For the adsorption experiments, 0.2 g of adsorbent was added to 50 mL of MB solutions with initial concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 mg/L contained in Erlenmeyer flasks. The tests were carried out in a batch type assembly at 200 rpm, constant temperature of 21 °C and optimal contact time determined from kinetic experiments. To determine the concentration, the absorbance was measured in a spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer instruments Lamda 40 UV/VIS spectrometer) at a wavelength of 664 nm.

The MB adsorption efficiency (% E) of the adsorption batch experiments was calculated by Equation (3):

$$\%E = \left[\frac{(C_0 - C_e)}{C_0} \right] * 100 \quad \text{Ec. (3)}$$

Where C_0 is the initial concentration of MB (mg/L), and C_e is the concentration of MB (mg/L) at equilibrium.

The amount of MB adsorbed or adsorption capacity at equilibrium (q_e , mg/L) for each experiment was calculated using Equation (4):

$$q_e = [(C_0 - C_e)/W] * V \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

Where q_e is the amount of MB adsorbed (mg/L) on the activated carbon at equilibrium, C_0 and C_e are the same as the previous ones, V is the experimental volume of the solution (L) and W is the weight of activated carbon used (g) [24].

2.5. Kinetic models

2.5.1. Lagergren kinetic models

The kinetic data were investigated using the pseudo first order and pseudo second order linear models shown in Equations (5) and (6), respectively.

$$\log(q_e - q_t) = \log(q_e) - \frac{k_{ad1}}{2.303} t \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_{ad2} * q_e^2} + \frac{1}{q_e} t \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

Where q_e and q_t are the adsorption capacities (MB adsorbed on the material in mg/g) at equilibrium and at any time t (min), respectively. K_{ad1} and K_{ad2} are the rate constants of the pseudo first order (min^{-1}) and pseudo second order ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) adsorption processes, respectively [24].

The initial adsorption rate for the pseudo second order Lagergren model, h_0 ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$), can be obtained from Equation (7):

$$h_0 = k_{ad2} * q_e^2 \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

2.5.2. Weber-Morris intraparticle diffusion model

The linear approach of the Weber-Morris kinetic model is presented in Equation (8).

$$q_t = k_D * t^{1/2} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

Where K_D is the intraparticle specific diffusion rate constant ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1/2}$), q_t is the adsorption capacity at any time (mg/g) and t is the contact time (min) [24].

2.6. Adsorption isotherms

2.6.1. Langmuir isotherm

The Langmuir isotherm model suggests that uptake occurs on a homogeneous surface by monolayer sorption without interaction between sorbed molecules. The model assumes uniform surface adsorption energies and no adsorbate transmigration in the surface plane [25].

In addition to the above, the Langmuir model has several assumptions among which are: (i) an adsorbent molecule occupies a single adsorption site on a homogeneous surface; (ii) when all adsorption sites are occupied the adsorbent becomes saturated (with a maximum capacity) and there will be no further adsorption, where the adsorbate forms a single-molecule thick surface (monolayer); (iii) the adsorption energy does not depend on the interactions between adjacent adsorbate molecules, that is, there is no interaction between them [23]. The linear form of the Langmuir isotherm equation is represented by Equation (9):

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{Q_{max} * K_L} + \frac{C_e}{Q_{max}} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

where C_e (mg/L) is the concentration at equilibrium, q_e (mg/L) is the adsorption capacity at equilibrium, Q_{max} is the maximum amount of adsorbate (mg/g) adsorbed at equilibrium when the adsorbent is saturated K_L is the constant of the Langmuir isotherm related to the affinity of the binding sites and the free energy of adsorption [23-25].

The essential characteristics of the Langmuir equation can be expressed in terms of a dimensionless separation factor, R_L , defined by Equation (10).

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_L C_0} \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

Where R_L is the dimensionless separation factor, K_L is the Langmuir isotherm constant and C_0 is the initial concentration of MB (mg/L). The R_L value implies that the adsorption is unfavorable ($R_L > 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$), favorable ($0 < R_L < 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$) [24-25].

2.6.2. Freundlich isotherm

The Freundlich isotherm is the oldest known relationship that describes the sorption equation. This empirical isotherm can be used for non-ideal sorption involving heterogeneous sorption. In addition to the above, the Freundlich model handles the following assumptions: (i) the adsorption energy decreases logarithmically with the linear increase in the number of occupied sites and (ii) there is no limit to the amount of adsorbate that can bind to the surface of the adsorbent [23]. The linear form of the Freundlich equation is shown in Equation (11) [25].

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + \frac{1}{N} \log C_e \quad \text{Eq. (11)}$$

Where q_e (mg/L) is the equilibrium adsorption capacity, C_e (mg/L) is the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate (MB), K_F is the Freundlich constant related to the adsorption capacity and $1/N$ is an empirical parameter related to adsorption intensity. $1/N$ is a parameter of heterogeneity. The smaller $1/N$, the greater the heterogeneity. If n is between one and ten, the adsorption process is favorable [26].

3. Results

3.1. Microwave-assisted chemical activation with H₃PO₄

3.1.1. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the signal/noise ratio (S/R)

In accordance with Taguchi's orthogonal design, twenty-seven different activated carbons were prepared by microwave-assisted chemical activation. In this sense, Table 10 shows the carbon yield results for each experiment that were used to predict the optimal conditions of the microwave assisted chemical activation process. The charcoal yield results were 93-99% for barley husk charcoal, 89-99% for cob charcoal, and 73-81% for agave charcoal.

The S/R ratio was examined by ANOVA to determine the relative significance of the S / R data obtained for the parameters of the microwave-assisted chemical activation process. According to [27], ANOVA allows determining the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables in a regression analysis. In this sense, the ANOVA results for the S/R ratio are shown in Table 11. The effects of the control factors on the S/R ratio of coal yields can be seen in Figure 1.

Table 10. Taguchi's experimental design of the L₉ orthogonal arrangement with the noise factors and the mean value of carbon yield obtained by microwave assisted chemical activation.

Arrangement of Control Factors					Noise Factor Fix		
Exp.	Control factors				Performance Coal (%p/p)		
	Factor A (%)	Factor B (min)	Factor C (W)	Factor D (cm ³ /min)	Barley hull	Corn cobs	Agave leaves
1	30	30	200	100	96.91	95.20	75.07
2	60	60	400	200	93.58	92.77	75.61
3	85	90	600	150	96.27	96.33	74.74
4	30	60	400	200	97.59	99.49	73.15
5	60	90	200	150	99.51	97.99	78.09
6	85	30	600	100	95.33	98.57	77.52
7	30	90	600	200	99.00	95.70	74.94
8	60	30	200	150	97.28	99.19	80.71
9	85	60	400	100	93.57	89.76	73.91

The F value indicates the statistical calculation of the effects of the control factor on the response. In this sense, the F value shown was obtained by comparing the variance associated with the residual variance. Therefore, the factor with the highest value of F is the most important factor affecting the performance of activated carbon in the chemical activation process. According to [28], an F ratio less than one suggests a negligible effect, a value close to two suggests a moderate effect, and if the F ratio is higher than four, the control factors have a strong and significant effect on the answer. In this regard, Table 11 shows that the concentration of the activating agent and the radiation time has a moderate effect, while the power of the microwaves has a strong and significant effect. In contrast, it is observed that the nitrogen flow rate has a negligible effect on the process.

Table 11. ANOVA of the S/R ratio for the activated carbon yields obtained by microwave-assisted chemical activation.

Source	DF ^a	S ^b	V ^c	F	S ^d	P ^e (%)	Average		
							Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Factor A (%)	2	0.06	0.03	2.03	0.03	8.92	38.77	38.97	38.86
Factor B (min)	2	0.08	0.04	2.81	0.05	15.64	38.84	39.00	38.77
Factor C (W)	2	0.16	0.08	5.73	0.14	40.86	39.00	38.68	38.93
Factor D (cm ³ /min)	2	0.03	0.01				38.81	38.85	38.95
Residual error	2	0.03	0.01		0.11	34.58			

degrees of freedom.

^b S: dev. stan.

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^c V: variance (S²).^d S': recalculated standard deviation neglecting the smallest variance.^e P: contribution percentage of each factor.

Figure 1. Effect of control factors on the S/R ratio of the activated carbon yield obtained by microwave-assisted chemical activation.

The F value indicates the statistical calculation of the effects of the control factor on the response. In this sense, the F value shown was obtained by comparing the variance associated with the residual variance. Therefore, the factor with the highest value of F is the most important factor affecting the performance of activated carbon in the chemical activation process. According to [28], an F ratio less than one suggests a negligible effect, a value close to two suggests a moderate effect, and if the F ratio is higher than four, the control factors have a strong and significant effect on the answer. In this regard, Table 11 shows that the concentration of the activating agent and the radiation time has a moderate effect, while the power of the microwaves has a strong and significant effect. In contrast, it is observed that the nitrogen flow rate has a negligible effect on the process.

3.2. Optimization of process parameters

In this study, the "highest best" type of S/R ratio was selected as the answer, as the highest yield of activated carbon is always desirable. Therefore, the higher S/R ratio corresponds to the optimal process conditions. Table 11 shows the mean S/R ratio for each level of the control factors, which was summarized as the S/R response. As can be seen in Figure 2, the optimal condition for the microwave-assisted chemical activation process with H₃PO₄ was the following:

- Factor A: [H₃PO₄] 60% (level 2)
- Factor B: Radiation time of 4 min (level 2)
- Factor C: 200 W power (level 1)
- Factor D: Nitrogen flow rate of 200 cm³/min (level 3)

For further study, activated carbon samples were prepared through confirmatory experiments using the levels indicated for the control factors, obtaining the following activated carbon yields under optimal conditions:

- 93.30 ± 0.31% for activated carbon from barley husk
- 95.62 ± 0.72% for activated charcoal from corn cob
- 71.77 ± 1.90% for activated carbon from agave leaves.

3.3. Effect of control factors on obtaining coal

According to what is reported in the literature, attempts have been made to develop microwave-based chemical activation processes. In this sense, the non-carbonized organic precursors of activated carbons impregnated with activating agents are generally poor microwave absorbers, making it difficult to heat them to high temperatures using microwaves. This problem can be solved using good microwave receivers such as carbonaceous materials [4].

One way to take advantage of the high microwave absorbing capacity of carbon materials is to use microwave heating to adapt their surface chemistry, introducing or removing functionalities on their surface. In the case of activated carbons, microwave heating has been used mainly for the rapid elimination of the functionalities present on the surface of the coal, especially oxygenated functionalities, and to produce, in just a few minutes, activated carbons with basic properties [4]. Thus, the main variables that have been studied in the microwave-assisted chemical activation process have been the power of the microwaves, the radiation time, the impregnation ratio of the activating agent and the flow rate of the entrainment gas [2].

The chemistry behind the chemical activation process depends on the reagent used. As indicated above, the objective of using an activating agent is to catalyze reactions that prevent carbon gasification and that promote the formation of porous structures by eliminating elements other than carbon [29].

Various reagents have been evaluated as activating agents by various investigators. Some of the most used have been ZnCl_2 , H_3PO_4 , KOH , K_2CO_3 and NaOH [2, 29]. During microwave-assisted chemical activation, activating agents are the main absorbers of microwave radiation in the initial phase of the activation process. It is important to note that if a chemical agent were not used, the carbonaceous raw materials would hardly be heated. In this way, after the development of the pore structure in the initial stages of the process, the activated carbon itself could efficiently receive the energy of microwave radiation during activation [2].

Some of the biomass materials are poor absorbers of microwave radiation. There-fore, the addition of good microwave receivers is essential to uniformly heat such materials. In chemical microwave activation, activating agents are expected to be the main absorbers of microwave radiation in the early part of the reaction to help reach the activation temperature quickly (500-800 ° C) [30]. The effect of control factors on the microwave-assisted activation process is described below.

3.4. Effect of H_3PO_4 as an activating agent

As previously stated, phosphoric acid has been used as an activating agent for lignocellulosic materials with high contents of volatile material and carbon contents of less than 90% [29]. Phosphoric acid is also one of the most prominent agents used in the production of activated carbons and has two important functions: (i) the promotion of the pyrolytic decomposition of the starting materials derived from their expansion and (ii) the organization of the structure crosslinked derived from the formation of crosslinks in the form of phosphate esters [2].

In addition to the above, the literature mentions that the porous structure and the surface area of the activated carbons obtained by phosphoric acid are highly influenced by the concentration used in the process and by the characteristics of the pre-cursor. In this research, the concentration of H_3PO_4 at level 2 was the optimum for obtaining activated carbons with the highest yields. In this sense, research reports that when phosphoric acid concentrations are too high, the dilation effect could be very in-tense, causing the collapse of the porous structure and a decrease in the surface area of activated carbons [29].

In addition to the above, microwave radiation can generate overheated areas (because of mineral impurities) within the carbon particles where the temperature is much higher than the total temperature of the sample, so the internal temperature of the sample can be tens or hundreds of degrees higher than the surface temperature due to the internal and volumetric nature of microwave heating. Therefore, this temperature difference can affect the stability and quality of the materials obtained and in other cases it can cause heterogeneous reactions between the sample and the gases in-volved in the reaction [2].

Studies such as those by [5] have reported the use of phosphoric acid as an activating agent in microwave-assisted processes. In this work, the surface area and the pore volume of activated carbons obtained from

bamboo were investigated using a microwave power of 350 W and 20 minutes of irradiation. The authors found that both the surface area and the pore volume increased with the increase in the impregnation ratio, attributing it to the penetration and occupation of potential sites by phosphoric acid, which helped the process of widening and opening of the pores in the materials. They indicated that an excessive dose of acid could form an insulating layer and not promote additional activation. Therefore, phosphoric acid in moderate concentrations works as a dehydrating agent and prevents the formation of tars and the formation of volatile cellulose products and other liquids that could block the pores of the carbonaceous material obtained; the volatile matter can then easily move through the pore channels and be released from the carbon surface gradually during the activation stage. This phenomenon leads to the consolidation of porous structures, an increase in the specific surface area and an increase in the adsorption capacity of the activated carbons obtained [2].

The literature also reports the use of phosphoric acid in microwave-assisted activation processes due to its dielectric characteristics. Thus, the studies by [30] demonstrated that the hydrogen bonding interaction between the phosphoric acid molecules in solution is responsible for their high viscosity and allows a high mobility of hydro-gen ions through the conduction of the Grotthus chain to through the hydrogen bonded structure. Therefore, liquids linked by hydrogen bond interactions, such as phosphoric acid, generally have high dielectric constants due to the orientation of the dipole that is favored by such interaction. The dielectric constant of 61 ± 12 confirms the associated character of phosphoric acid and with it the character of microwave receptor [31].

In the microwave-assisted activated carbon production process, the dielectric properties are dependent on frequency, composition and temperature. Therefore, the presence of an electrolyte such as phosphoric acid improves the ability of the material to be heated using microwaves; This effect, added to the delocalization of π electrons in the polycyclic aromatic structures of carbon materials, improves the capacity of the material to be heated by microwaves [32]. Based on the above discussion, the 60% H_3PO_4 concentration (at a medium level) is justified for this investigation. The relationship of this concentration with the other process parameters will be explained below.

3.5. Effect of microwave power

According to research, it is almost impossible to accurately measure the temperature of the sample during microwave radiation. That is why the microwave power has been used as a variable in the preparation process instead of the temperature of the sample. The microwave power can develop pores that can be restricted or blocked by deposits of tarry substances, giving rise to highly uniform and well-developed porous structures in the activated carbon obtained [2].

Very high microwave power levels cause a faster reaction rate between the activating agent and the precursor, which promotes the development of the pore structure and active sites [2]. Some researchers have specifically studied the effects of micro-wave power on the adsorption capacity of activated carbons. For example, [12] studied the effects of the power level with a constant impregnation ratio of 1.25 (% p/p) and an irradiation time of 5 min on the adsorption capacity of activated carbons prepared by the method. Microwave from orange peels using K_2CO_3 as activating agent. They observed that at low microwave power levels of 90 and 180 W, iodine number and methylene blue adsorption capacity remained almost unchanged. This lack of change that they observed indicated that there was no continuous reaction (activation) between the carbon prepared from the carbonization step and the activating agent at these low potency levels in the activation process. However, at 360 and 600 W, the methylene blue adsorption capacity showed a progressive increase. The authors proposed that the combined effect of volumetric and internal heating by microwave irradiation enhanced the formation of porous structures during chemical activation. They also found that at microwave power levels beyond the optimal value, the adsorption capacity of methylene blue progressively decreased due to the destruction of the pore structures by higher levels of irradiation.

Liu et al. [5] used bamboo to produce carbons activated with phosphoric acid as a chemical agent by the microwave-induced method. They found a remarkable decrease in micropore formation at 400 W, while mesopore formation increased significantly. The development of mesopores appears to be preferred at

higher levels of microwave power. It was explained that, at high power levels, phosphoric acid showed an intense reaction with carbon, which facilitates the development of the pore structure. The activation process promotes the removal of some components (such as tars and volatile matter) at the higher temperatures that result from increased microwave power. Therefore, the power of 200 W in level 1 is justified as the optimum for the activation process, since with this power it is possible to favor the reaction between phosphoric acid and carbon that leads to the highest yields of activated carbon.

3.6. Effect of radiation time

The microwave method heats evenly with a fast-heating rate, so the sample can acquire more active sites in a shorter time by opening previously inaccessible pores, creating new pores through selective activation, and widening and fusing existing pores through the breakdown of the pore wall. These changes in porosity result in a high activation efficiency [2]. The variables associated with the production of activated carbon by microwave heating have different and significant effects on the pore structure.

The BET surface decreases with the increase in the activation time above the optimal microwave radiation time, possibly because the agent is not used yet when the BET surface reaches the maximum value and the increase in the activation time induces the destruction of some structures microporous, which leads to the decrease of the surface [2]. In this investigation the analysis of the S/R relation of the data indicated that the optimal level for the radiation time was level 2 corresponding to 4 minutes (medium level).

Foo and Hameed [12] obtained activated carbons based on orange peel using a microwave-induced method with K_2CO_3 as a chemical agent at a constant impregnation ratio of 1.25 (% w/p) and microwave power of 600 W at different times. activation. They observed that the methylene blue adsorption capacity increased from 193.81 to 297.16 mg/g when the microwave radiation time increased from 4 to 6 min. They explain that, by prolonging the activation time, the reaction with the activation agent is favored and the loss of volatile matter increases. Therefore, the adsorption capacity increases through the development of porosity and pore structure. In contrast, they attributed a slight decrease in adsorption capacity (26.84 mg/g) at 7 min of radiation time due to an increase in temperature and to the opening of micropores and meso-pores as the activation process progressed. They concluded that the increase in activation time apparently increased the mean pore diameter. Additionally, they indicate that the local superheating points produced by the additional heating led to the retraction of the channels formed in the activated carbon structure. Therefore, the accessibility of the activated carbon sites was drastically reduced, which resulted in the reduction of the adsorption capacity. Therefore, for the purposes of the chemical activation process, the radiation time of 4 minutes (level 2) is justified as the optimal one for the process, since with this it is possible to favor the reactions between the phosphoric acid and the carbon precursor. To obtain the best performance, promote the expansion of the precursor and consolidate the porous structure without collapsing in the activated carbons obtained.

3.7. Effect of nitrogen flow rate

The speed of the entrained gas flow is another parameter that influences the process of obtaining activated carbons. Thus, moderate to high amounts of vapors are formed during heat treatment and if these vapors are not purged from the system, they may themselves involve side reactions and may change the nature and composition of the products. Thus, an increase in the gas flow rate pushes the vapors out of the reaction zone resulting in the shortening of the residence time of the released vapors. In this sense, the literature mentions that the reduction of the residence time of the re-released vapors does not allow the volatile components of the biomass to start the re-polymerization process, so the volatile components are quickly expelled, which causes the carbon yield to decrease [33]. For the purposes of this study, the analysis of the S/R ratio of the data indicated that the optimal condition for the nitrogen flow rate was 200 cm^3/min , which corresponds to the highest level used. This condition is suitable for the microwave-assisted chemical activation process, since this speed is sufficient to take most of the vapors out of the reaction zone between phosphoric acid and lignocellulosic materials, resulting in obtaining high yields of Coal. In addition, this condition is also justified since the phosphoric acid promotes the gradual release of the volatile material

from the precursors in less time during the microwave-assisted activation process, which is why high nitrogen flow rates were necessary to obtain high carbon yields.

3.8. Characterization of activated carbons obtained under optimal conditions.

3.8.1. Proximal analysis

Table 12 shows the proximal analysis results for activated carbons obtained by chemical activation with phosphoric acid. Ash contents of less than 10% are observed for activated carbons from corn cob and agave leaves, and 12% for barley husk. In relation to this, studies indicate that the ash content is an important parameter since it defines the quality of the precursor in combustion when determining the content of non-combustible matter present [34]. Therefore, a low ash content is desirable.

Table 12. Proximal analysis of activated carbons obtained under optimal conditions of micro-wave-assisted

Raw material	Fixed Carbon (%w/w)		Volatile matter (%w/w)		Ash (%w/w)		Moisture (%w/w)	
	Precursor	Coal	Precursor	Coal	Precursor	Coal	Precursor	Coal
Barley	4.86	46.79	79.84	35.89	7.91	11.92	7.38	5.40
Corn cob	6.09	54.79	84.46	35.49	2.54	3.73	6.91	5.99
Agave	10.65	55.33	79.30	37.56	9.92	1.12	7.38	5.99

chemical activation and precursors.

Regarding the volatile content, the literature mentions that they are compounds released during the initial phase of a process and are made up of different amounts of hydrogen, carbon oxides, methane, and other low molecular weight hydrocarbons. Volatile matter is partly responsible for the existing pores in the structures of carbonaceous materials, since, after being subjected to high temperatures, the volatile material detaches, leaving a pore where it was. In this sense, Ioannidou and Zabaniotou [35] indicate that in the processes for obtaining activated carbons the gradual elimination of gases and liquids at low temperatures is of utmost importance to obtain low volatilization and high yields of carbon which is important for the preparation of activated carbons. Therefore, the volatile matter content is another important parameter as it provides an indication of the reactivity and ease of ignition of an organic material. Volatile matter contents of 36% for barley husk charcoal, 35% for cob and 38% for agave leaves were determined. These results, compared with the percentages found in the coals obtained by means of chemical activation by conventional heating, are observed to be similar, and are higher than those determined in the coals obtained by pyrolysis, which is due to the inhibitory effect of phosphoric acid for the formation of volatile cellulose products.

In relation to the content of fixed carbon, significant enrichment in this parameter is observed in the three coals after the chemical activation process after the release of volatile material, mainly in the barley husk compared to the other activation methods. As can be seen, the fixed carbon contents were higher than those obtained in the coals obtained by pyrolysis and chemical activation by conventional heating. In this sense, fixed carbon contents of 47% for activated carbon from barley husk and 55% for agave and cob were determined. As can be seen, barley husk was the precursor that presented the lowest carbon enrichment, and agave and cob were the ones that presented the highest fixed carbon content after the activation process. This trend was to be expected since the gradual and controlled loss of volatile matter because of phosphoric acid resulted in the carbon enrichment of the coals obtained after the micro-wave-assisted chemical activation process.

3.8.2. Elemental analysis

Table 13 shows the results of elemental analysis of carbonaceous materials obtained by microwave-assisted chemical activation. Carbon contents of 61% are shown for barley husk, 69% for cob husk and 68% for agave husk.

When compared to those obtained for raw materials, these values are higher only for activated cob and agave carbons, and lower for barley husk. In the latter material, the low carbon content was attributed to its high content of inorganic material. Similar behaviors were presented in the content of H, N and O. In this

way, contents of 3% for hydrogen, less than 1% for nitrogen, and 27-35% for oxygen were observed in the materials.

Table 13. Elemental analysis of coals obtained under optimal conditions of microwave-assisted chemical

Raw material	%C		%H		%N		%O	
	Precursor	Coal	Precursor	Coal	Precursor	Coal	Precursor	Coal
Barley husk	42.08	61.09	6.32	3.23	0.65	0.18	50.95	35.50
Corn cob	43.93	68.84	6.12	3.13	0.58	0.35	49.37	27.68
Agave	44.63	68.34	5.83	3.90	0.02	0.52	49.52	27.24

activation and precursors.

3.8.3. IR spectroscopy

The FT-IR spectra of activated carbon from barley husk, activated carbon from cob and activated carbon from agave leaves are shown in Figure 2. The bands at 3442 cm^{-1} and 2926 cm^{-1} for carbon from barley husk At 3425 cm^{-1} and 2935 cm^{-1} for corn cob charcoal, at 3425 cm^{-1} and 2925 cm^{-1} for agave leaf charcoal were observed. The band around 3400 cm^{-1} was assigned to the O-H oxygen bonded hydrogen bonding tension. The hydrophilic tendency of the three carbons was reflected in the broad absorption band, which is related to the -OH groups present in the groups of aliphatic or aromatic alcohols present in their components. The band around 2900 cm^{-1} was assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric C-H stress of saturated aliphatic compounds. These two tension bands correspond to the aliphatic fragments present in the carbonaceous materials obtained.

Bands in the $1375\text{-}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range were assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric C-H strains in methyl. The band at 1631 cm^{-1} (most intense) for barley husk charcoal, at 1614 cm^{-1} for corn cob charcoal and at 1613 cm^{-1} for agave charcoal are corresponding to the CC bonds in acyclic compounds and conjugates.

Figure 2. FTIR spectrum of activated carbons obtained by microwave-assisted chemical activation.

The bands located from $1457\text{ to }1163\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for barley charcoal, from $1459\text{ to }1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for cob charcoal, and from $1437\text{ to }1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for agave charcoal, are representative of deformation vibrations and DC voltage on aromatic rings, plus those of C = O and CH. This band region is indicative of the carbon enrichment of the three precursors after heat treatment under optimal process conditions. Bands in the $1375\text{-}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range were assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric C-H strains in methyl.

The bands at $768, 672, 642$ and 610 cm^{-1} for barley charcoal, at $761, 688, 658$ and 597 cm^{-1} for cob charcoal, and at $766, 692, 658$ and 619 cm^{-1} for agave charcoal are indicative of out of plane deformation of the CH bond of alkenes and benzene-derived compounds. The spectrum of barley coal differs from the other two,

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with three intense bands being observed at 1083 cm^{-1} , 799 cm^{-1} and 458 cm^{-1} , of which the first two are indicative of the vibrations of the Si-O- bonds. Yes, and the third is indicative of the bending of the O-Si-O bonds. These bands are consistent with those reported by [36], who mention that in the FTIR spectrum for barley husk, the Si-O-Si vibration and tension bands appear in the $420\text{-}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $950\text{-}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions, respectively. The presence of these bands in barley husk carbon is due to the fact that, after the activation process, the ash content was concentrated, specifically from 7.91% in the precursor to 11% in the activated carbon. This finding is consistent with the studies by [36, 37], who report silica contents of 80% for barley husk and 60% for rice husk as the main component, respectively (natural tendency of grasses to absorb silicon from the soil where they are found).

Finally, because of the activation process with H_3PO_4 , bands for the deformation vibrations of the γPOC (phosphate esters) and γPO (phosphate) bonds were observed, respectively at 1073 and 1030 cm^{-1} for activated cob carbon, and 1068 and 1039 cm^{-1} for agave activated carbon. These bands were not accurately determined in the spectrum of barley activated carbon as they overlapped with the bands of the Si-O-Si bonds.

3.8.4. Scanning electron microscopy

The morphological changes obtained in the three materials after the chemical activation process were observed by means of scanning electron microscopy. Figures 3a-c show the morphology of barley husk coals, corn cobs and agave leaves. It was observed that the activated carbon from barley husk (Figure 3-a) shows a significant mesoporous morphology formed in the cross section of the fibers, as well as a large number of irregularly shaped channels in the longitudinal section. For cob charcoal, Figure 3-b shows a morphology made up of a large number of channels of more less regular shapes and sizes in the longitudinal section of the fibers; meso and macroporous structures are observed. In Figure 3-c, it can be seen that significant meso and macroporous structures were formed in the agave charcoal in the cross section of the fibers, as well as channels of regular shapes and irregular sizes in their longitudinal section. As indicated above, the physical changes observed after the activation process with phosphoric acid of the three precursors can be related to the structure and arrangement of their constituents, which are distributed in different layers of biopolymers: the middle lamella is mainly made up of lignin. and cell walls are made up of cellulose and hemicellulose chains that form threadlike aggregates known as microfibrils [29]. In this sense, the analysis of the samples of carbonaceous materials showed significant meso and macroporous structures formed by the remaining middle lamella layer and by charred cellulose and hemicellulose.

Based on the above observations and on the phosphoric acid activation mechanism described above, some of the processes that are happening during the activation of the three precursors can be inferred. In this sense, once the H_3PO_4 fuses as the temperature increases, it begins to react with the precursor promoting dehydration reactions. This dehydration mechanism decomposes the biopolymer generating short chains of biopolymers that have a weaker interaction with other chains, which facilitates the sliding of the polymer chains with the consequent formation of the fluid phase.

Figure 3. Photomicrographs of activated carbons of (a) barley husk, (b) corn cobs and (c) agave leaves obtained by microwave-assisted chemical activation.

Next, the short interaction between H_3PO_4 and the terminal OH groups of the chains of the generated low molecular weight biopolymers promotes the formation of phosphate and polyphosphate bridging bonds that causes the expansion and crosslinking of the carbon matrix resulting in consolidation of an accessible pore structure after acid removal in the final washing process. It is important to point out that, while the consolidation of the carbonaceous structure takes place, the gases generated within the fibers try to emerge through the molten phase, so that the diffusion of these gases through the fluid phase develops pathways. that at a certain point of the activation they become solid, being responsible for the consolidation of porous structures in the activated carbons obtained.

3.8.5. X-ray diffraction

Figures 4a-c show the X-ray diffraction patterns of the three activated carbons obtained. In the diffraction patterns of the three carbons, the amorphous responses are observed from $2\theta = 10^\circ$ as a result of the thermal treatment, forming a wide and higher intensity peak that can be attributed to the formation of cross-linked graphitic structures derived from the formation of phosphate and polyphosphate bridging bonds as a result of the interaction between H_3PO_4 and the terminal OH groups of the chains of low molecular weight biopolymers that cause the expansion and crosslinking of the carbon matrix that results in the consolidation of porous structures in the materials.

This is indicative of the presence of carbon-pore interfaces in the activated carbons obtained. For the three materials, peaks were observed for 2θ around 25° and 45° , which correspond to the reflections (002) and (100) of the graphite structure, respectively. According to [38], the presence of these peaks is indicative of graphitization processes carried out during activation. Therefore, it can be established that the graphitization was moderate in the activation process since the peaks are not well defined.

Specifically, the broad peak assigned to reflection (002) can be the result of incomplete development of microcrystalline structures, and the peak assigned to reflection (100) can be attributed to the development of graphitic crystallites during treatment. This second peak was more intense in cob charcoal (Figure 4-b), followed by agave charcoal (Figure 4-c) and less intense in barley husk charcoal (Figure 4-a). Based on the foregoing, it is established that the peaks observed in the diffractograms are indicative of the formation of graphite layers as microcrystals in the carbonaceous materials obtained.

3.8.6. Thermogravimetric analysis

The thermogravimetric analyzes showed similar thermal decomposition curves for the three activated carbons obtained. A first peak (endothermic) was observed in the range of $90-110^\circ C$, probably due to the amount of water that was added during the impregnation and that did not completely evaporate in the drying stage of the materials. and, to the condensation of phosphoric acid, which begins around $104^\circ C$ [39].

The peaks indicative of the degradation of the lignocellulosic constituents changed very little and were distributed over a wide range of temperatures after the activation process with phosphoric acid. Therefore, the changes in the thermal decomposition profile of the impregnated materials are explained by the dehydration of the activating agent during the process, which favors the release of a water molecule as explained in previous paragraphs at the expense of the release of oxygenated organic compounds or hydrocarbons, thus favoring the formation of aromatic compounds less susceptible to volatilization.

The previous observation means that during the process of obtaining activated carbons that contain phosphorus, with the use of microwave heating, the structure of the samples is altered since the microwaves favor the cross-linking reactions between the carbonaceous material and the acid. during the activation process, in such a way that the highly developed porous structures in the obtained carbonaceous materials become less resistant (collapse) at elevated temperatures. This aspect constitutes an important difference with respect to the thermogravimetric behavior observed in activated carbons resulting from chemical activation by conventional heating.

3.8.7. Zeta potential

The zeta potential is a physical parameter that can be used to quantify the electrical potential of the surface of a solid particle [40]. The zeta potential results for bar-ley husk carbon, corn cob carbon and agave carbon are shown in Table 14. In this sense, the electrokinetic behavior of activated carbon in solution is one of the most important properties in the characterization of these materials. Likewise, it is important to highlight that these materials are amphoteric in nature due to the presence of various functional groups on their surfaces and a system of delocalized π electrons that give them basic properties [41]. By measurements of the zeta potential, it was determined that the surface charge of the three precursors and their activated carbons is anionic, obtaining values of -27.6 mV for barley husk and -16.44 mV for their activated carbon, of -30.92 mV for cob and of -14.53 mV for its activated charcoal, and values of -22.0 mV for agave and -18.57 for its activated charcoal. A certain decrease in the ani-on potential is observed for activated carbons.

The explanation for the notable variation can be correlated with the car-bon/oxygen ratio, which increased in the three activated carbons, significantly in those of corn cobs and agave leaves. This observed increase in the carbon/oxygen ratio in activated carbons is attributed to the degree of carbon enrichment after the activation process, which is related to the presence of polycyclic aromatic structures (delocalized π electron system) in the materials that contribute to the presence of anionic surface charges.

On the other hand, the moderate decrease in the anionic zeta potential is also attributed to the effect of phosphorus as a graphitization inhibitor derived from the formation of cross-linked bonds such as phosphate esters during the activation process, which result in a highly developed porous structure a At the expense of the formation of graphitic crystallites of lesser scope and with fewer delocalized π electrons, which translates into activated carbons with less intense anionic surface charges. In addition to the above, microwave treatment also has special effects on the surface chemistry of prepared activated carbon since it considerably increases the car-bon/oxygen ratio as shown in Table 14, eliminating the functional groups that contain acidic oxygen present in the components. volatile resulting in basic activated carbons [2]. From these results it is established that the zeta potential values are indicative of anionic surfaces in the activated carbons obtained and therefore, they can be effective for adsorption processes of positively charged molecules or ions.

Table 14. Zeta potential values and C/O ratio of activated carbons obtained by microwave-assisted chemical activation compared with the study precursors.

Raw material	Zeta potential (mV)		Carbon/Oxygen Ratio	
	Precursor	Chemical activation with microwaves	Precursor	Chemical activation with microwaves
Barley husk	-27.60±2.13	-16.44±0.26	0.82	1.72
Corn cob	-30.92±1.68	-14.53±1.36	0.89	2.49
Agave	-22.00±1.10	-18.57±0.38	0.90	2.51

3.9. Discussion of the effect of microwaves on silicon oxides present in barley husk

The literature indicates that dielectric materials such as alumina, silicon oxides, and other metal oxides are transparent to microwaves at room temperature. The microwave-assisted process compared to conventional heating (conduction, convection and radiation) transfers energy through interactions at the molecular level between the electromagnetic field and materials, so that the heating occurs volumetrically creating a temperature distribution with a maximum in the center of the particle. As dis-cussed above, microwave heating can be coupled with certain materials that have excellent dielectric properties such as carbonaceous materials. In this sense, materials such as activated carbons are capable of absorbing microwave energy in a volumetric way to transform it into heat from inside them [42].

As mentioned above, dielectric materials like silicates are microwave transparent at room temperature. However, as the temperature of these materials increases, their microwave absorption capacity increases considerably and can be greatly increased by the action of some additives or by the presence of water. The

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presence of these constituents in carbon matrices (barley husk pyrolyzed) promotes a rapid increase in temperature at the same time as its microwave adsorption capacity increases [42].

Several mechanisms have been proposed for the growth of a one-dimensional nanostructure, such as vapor-liquid, vapor-solid and solid-liquid-solid mechanisms [43]. According to the results obtained in the microwave-assisted process, Figure 5 shows a mechanism proposed by [43] on the effect of microwaves on silicon compounds in carbon matrices.

Figure 5-a indicates the pyrolyzed barley husk sample with its inorganic constituents represented mainly by SiO_2 being heated with microwave radiation. Agree [43], as the temperature increases, the vapor-liquid mechanism occurs. In the first stage, as shown in Figure 5-a, the mixture of barley husk pyrolyzed with the activating agent was exposed to microwave heating. When exposed to microwave irradiation, the barley husk pyrolyzed is capable of absorbing irradiation as indicated by the red arrows (Figure 5-a). This carbon material can be heated by microwaves due to delocalized π electrons, which can move freely within the polycyclic aromatic structures derived from the formation of $\text{C} = \text{C}$ bonds in the pyrolyzed.

Figure 5. Effect of microwave heating on SiO_2 compounds present in activated barley husk carbons.

During the process, as the carbon continues to absorb the microwave energy, the kinetic energy of the delocalized π electrons increases and therefore each carbon atom begins to vibrate. These actions cause heat to be generated volumetrically after absorbing microwave energy, and thus the temperature of carbon materials and their inorganic constituents increases. In this sense, it is known that SiO_2 is a microwave reflector and, therefore, the energy supplied during the process by microwaves cannot penetrate it due to its non-polar characteristics [43]. In addition to this, the structure of SiO_2 is linked by strong covalent bonds between the Si atom and O, so its intermolecular force is very strong, which means that microwave energy cannot be absorbed by these compounds. Therefore, in the microwave-assisted activation process of the barley husk pyrolyzed, the SiO_2 particles were heated by conduction of thermal energy from carbon.

For the second stage, Figure 5-b shows that carbon reacts with SiO_2 particles as temperature increases to form SiO gas (green arrows) and carbon monoxide (CO) gas (yellow arrows). The chemical reaction that describes this stage is shown in Equation (12), which is highly endothermic and requires high temperatures to be carried out. It should be noted that the excess carbon present in the pyrolysates used as raw materials can create a reducing atmosphere to avoid the oxidation of the products and favor the process. Studies indicate that this process is favored with the use of catalysts. In this investigation, no catalyst was added to the sample, so the transition metals (such as iron oxides) present in their inorganic constituents as impurities could act as catalysts during the process as reported by [42].

The process described above could explain the notable decrease in the ash content of activated carbon resulting from the microwave-assisted process (11%) compared to the ash content obtained in the other two methods of this investigation (30-40%). Likewise, this behavior would be responsible for the fact that more

carbon is available for the crosslinking reactions with phosphoric acid that are promoted by the effect of microwaves, favoring the consolidation of highly developed porous structures in the last stage (Figure 5- c) and more active sites (IR spectrum). In the same way, the crystallites of silicon oxides observed in the XRD pattern of the barley husk pyrolyzed decreased markedly after the microwave-assisted process due to Equation (12), obtaining highly developed highly amorphous and porous structures.

3.10. Evaluation of the adsorptive capacity of methylene blue

3.10.1. Effect of contact time

Figures 6a-c and 6d-f show the graphs of experimental adsorption capacity [q_e (mg/g)] and removal efficiency (% E) of methylene blue (MB), respectively, for the carbonaceous materials derived from each method. activation. The kinetics were obtained at different contact times for 180 minutes with a 0.2 g adsorbent dose, an initial adsorbate concentration of 50 mg/L, a pH of 8 and a temperature of 22 °C.

The kinetic results show that for carbonaceous materials obtained by pyrolysis, equilibrium is reached after 120 min in all cases. Since the pyrolysis process led to megaporous structures that represent a smaller surface to adsorb, the materials obtained by this process require a moderate time to reach equilibrium. Figure 6-a indicates that the material with the highest experimental adsorption capacity is agave carbon with 80.52 mg/g, followed by barley husk carbon with 37.08 mg/g, and lastly cob carbon with 24.89 mg/g. g for an initial concentration of 50 mg/L of MB. In Figure 6-d it is observed that agave charcoal presented the highest removal efficiency with 64.41% followed by barley husk charcoal with 29.66% and lastly cob charcoal with 19.91% for the same concentration initial coloring.

In contrast, it is observed that, for activated carbons derived from chemical activation with phosphoric acid, equilibrium was reached at 90 min in all cases. Thus, Figure 6-b shows that the material that obtained the highest adsorption capacity was agave activated carbon with 106.77 mg/g. The activated carbons of barley husk and cob had similar adsorption capacities with values of 80.67 mg/g and 79.11 mg/g, respectively. Figure 6-e shows that agave activated carbon is the material with the highest MB removal efficiency with 89.29%, followed by activated barley carbon with 64.54% and by activated cob carbon with 63.29%. After the chemical activation process with phosphoric acid, the adsorption capacity and efficiency increased considerably for the three adsorbents since their effects lead to the formation of mesoporous and macroporous structures, which means that they require less time to reach equilibrium.

In the case of the materials obtained through the microwave-assisted activation process, it is observed that equilibrium is reached after 180 min in all cases. The in-crease in the time to reach equilibrium is attributed to the fact that this process al-lowed obtaining more uniform and highly developed meso and macroporous structures that represent surface areas superior to those of the two previous methods, and in which the dye adsorption process takes more time to reach equilibrium. Figure 6-c shows that the material that obtained the highest adsorption capacity was activated carbon from barley husk with 100.51 mg/g followed by activated carbon from cob with 93.32 mg/g and lastly activated carbon from agave with 89.26 mg/g.

In addition to this, Figure 6-f indicates that activated carbon from barley husk is the material with the highest removal efficiency of MB with 80.41%, followed by activated carbon from cob with 74.66% and activated carbon from agave with 71.41%. It can be observed that after the microwave-assisted chemical activation process, the adsorption capacity and efficiency increased considerably for activated carbons from barley and cob; however, these parameters decreased for agave activated charcoal.

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Figure 6. Kinetics of methylene blue obtained with 0.2 g of adsorbent derived from (a) and (d) pyrolysis, (b) and (e) chemical activation, and (c) and (f) microwave-assisted chemical activation; initial concentration of 50 mg/L, particle diameter of 1.5-0.25 mm, pH = 8 and T = 22 °C.

In general terms, it was observed that the adsorption capacity increases very rapidly in the initial period of time and as it passes it becomes constant, in such a way that equilibria were reached from 120 minutes for the coals obtained by pyrolysis, from 90 minutes for those of chemical activation and 180 minutes for those obtained through the microwave-assisted activation process. The difference in times can be attributed on the one hand to the porous structure developed in each activation process and on the other hand to the availability and quantity of active sites for the adsorption process in the materials.

Generally, at the time of adsorption, the adsorbent surface comes into contact with the dye molecules and the outer surface of the adsorbent begins to be occupied. As time passes, more and more dye molecules are adsorbed, and after a certain period of time, the outer surface becomes saturated. After saturation of the outer surface, the dye molecules are adsorbed on the inner surface of the adsorbent particle, but the time required to reach the inside of an adsorbent particle is comparatively longer as individual dye molecules have to travel one long distance resulting in various mass transfer resistors. This observation is consistent with that reported by [23] for adsorption processes of methylene blue on activated carbons.

In addition to the above, the change in the adsorption rate observed in the kinetic studies may be due to the fact that initially all the adsorbent sites are empty as previously mentioned and also because the MB concentration gradient is very high. Subsequently, it is observed that the adsorption rate decreases due to the decrease in the number of vacant sites of the adsorbent and the concentration of dye. The decrease in the adsorption rate, particularly in the final stage of the experiments, indicates the possible formation of an MB monolayer in the adsorbents which can be attributed to the lack of available active sites that are required for further adsorption after they are reaches equilibrium.

Nieto-Delgado [44] has mentioned that the surface electrical charge of an activated carbon depends on the pH of the solution, therefore the interactions and the adsorption capacity of the material can be optimized by modifying its surface chemistry and/or the pH of the medium. In this sense, it was previously stated that activated carbon has acidic and basic sites that coexist on its surface, which can be protonated or deprotonated according to the pH of the solution that is in contact with them. Thus, in this study the pH at which the adsorption experiments with methylene blue were carried out was 8 (slightly basic). According to Hameed et al. [25], at basic pH the cationic form of methylene blue is the predominant one and its adsorption is shown to favor adsorbents with anionic surface charges. This was convenient for adsorption processes, since by zeta potential measurements it was determined that the carbonaceous materials obtained have anionic surface charges which are suitable for adsorption processes of positively charged molecules such as methylene blue.

For the adsorption processes with the coals obtained by pyrolysis, a marked difference was observed in the efficiency and adsorption capacity between the agave charcoal and those of barley and cob husk. Thermogravimetric and lignocellulosic constituent analyzes determined that agave is the precursor with the highest cellulose content. In this sense, it is known that the intramolecular dehydration of cellulose (300-350 °C) carried out in thermochemical processes (such as those in this research) leads to the formation of C = C bonds that promote the formation of benzene rings that make up the polycyclic aromatic structure in activated carbons. This establishment can be directly related to the intense and broad band observed for this bond in the IR spectrum of agave charcoal (1420 cm⁻¹). It was also observed that this precursor leads its constituents towards the formation of C = O functionalities which are consistent with the shoulder band that appears in its IR spectrum around 1620 cm⁻¹. Up to this point, these two functional groups contribute to the presence of anionic surface charges on all three materials. Likewise, it was also determined that agave charcoal is the material that presents the highest intensity in the band corresponding to O-H functionalities (3400 cm⁻¹) which represent sources of acidity on the surface of coals. These bands were more intense in the agave charcoal, followed by that of barley husk and less intense in the cob material.

Most surface oxygenated groups on activated carbons can establish an acid-base balance when in contact with aqueous solutions. Thus, acidic groups tend to release protons, especially in basic media, while basic groups tend to capture them when found in acidic media. In this way, positive or negative charges can appear on the surface of the carbon. As indicated, in this study the working pH was slightly basic so it can be deduced that under this condition part of the OH surface functionalities of the coals are capable of releasing a proton to the medium, leaving an electric charge on the surface of the carbon negative jointly promoting anionic surface charges of greater intensity which can interact with the cationic molecules present in the solution that in this case correspond to the chemical structures of methylene blue in its cationic form. That is why under these conditions, adsorption is favored.

Therefore, the conditions of the previous paragraph added to the effects of the resonance of the π electrons of the aromatic carbon rings that are related to positive charges, and the presence of basic functional groups allow methylene blue to be adsorbed in most of the active sites on the surface of materials. That is why the greater adsorption capacities and dye removal efficiencies were presented with greater intensity in the adsorption tests with agave charcoal. This material is followed by barley husk carbon with lower adsorption capacities, such behavior is attributed to the high content of inorganic material consisting mainly of amorphous silicon oxides that constitute an interference towards the development of polycyclic aromatic structures given their low content. Carbon also acts as interferences in the adsorption process by covering active centers in the material, preventing the access of methylene blue molecules to them. Lastly, there is cob carbon whose majority composition in hemicelluloses (very labile structures that decompose easily at temperatures above 220 °C) makes this material develop fewer active sites on its surface (under optimal pyrolysis conditions) because of its low cellulose content. In this case, it would be convenient to operate under conditions that make it possible to take advantage of the carbon present in the hemicelluloses of this last precursor as a secondary aspect of research to the results obtained.

The trend observed in the adsorption capacity and removal efficiency was inverse to that obtained for the zeta potential, which can be attributed to the amount of hydroxyl groups (acid sites) that are present on the

surface of the materials. Based on these results, it is established that this parameter can only be used to quantify the electrical potential of the surface of the solid particles of the carbonaceous materials obtained, but not to relate it to the efficiency and adsorption capacity that the materials will have in solution.

In relation to the adsorption processes with the coals obtained by chemical activation with phosphoric acid, it was observed that agave charcoal is the one with the highest removal efficiency and AM adsorption capacity, followed by that of barley husk and lastly for the cob charcoal. A considerable increase in both parameters is observed with respect to the pyrolysis method. This increase in adsorption is attributed to the effects produced by phosphoric acid to generate mesoporous and macroporous structures that result from the expansion of the precursor caused by the formation of cross-linked phosphate esters during the activation process, so that the surface in-creases and active sites are increased in the materials. This process is much more marked in agave charcoal given its high cellulose content, followed by that of barley husk given its high content of inorganic material that represents an uncontrolled interference given the nature of the precursor that can cover active centers in the mate-rial preventing the access of the dye molecules to them, and finally the charcoal of corn cobs due to its low content of cellulose and high content of hemicelluloses, as explained previously.

Finally, it was observed that after the microwave-assisted chemical activation process the adsorption capacity and efficiency increased considerably for activated carbons from barley husk and cob and decreased for activated agave carbon. This is because the microwave assisted activation method has the effect of increasing the C/O ratio by removing acidic oxygen containing functional groups. Since this process started from the carbonized materials obtained from pyrolysis, the carbonized agave is the one with the highest content of such functional groups based on its IR spectrum, followed by that of barley husk and cob. as a last resort. Therefore, under the experimental conditions set forth, microwaves modify oxygenated functionalities mainly in agave material. That is why the active sites of this material decrease, thus reducing its adsorption capacity and removal efficiency towards methylene blue. In relation to activated carbon from barley husk, a significant increase in its adsorption capacity is observed (compared to that of the two previous methods), which is attributed to possible interactions of inorganic elements from amorphous silicon oxides and other oxides. metals present in their inorganic constituents (impurities) that can promote a catalytic effect that favors the formation of polycyclic aromatic systems (increases the C/O ratio) and the consolidation of well-developed porous structures with a large amount of oxygenated active sites, as observed in IR spectrum. The effect of microwaves on silicates leading to increased porosity and active sites in activated carbon from barley husk discussed above allow to explain the increase in adsorption capacities and removal efficiencies of methylene blue in experiments performed with this material.

3.10.2. Effect of initial concentration

Figures 7a-c and 7d-f show the graphs of the effect of the initial concentration of methylene blue on the adsorption capacity [q_e (mg/g)] and removal efficiency (% E), respectively, for the derived carbonaceous materials. of each activation method. The results were obtained with the contact times determined in the kinetic experiments, with an adsorbent dose of 0.2 g, an initial adsorbate concentration of 10-50 mg/L, a pH of 8 and a temperature of 22 °C.

The graphs show that the initial dye concentration has a significant and moderate effect on methylene blue adsorption and the effects are shown in Figures 7a-c. In these graphs it is observed that the adsorption capacity at equilibrium increases with in-creasing concentration in all cases.

Figure 7-a shows that agave charcoal obtained by pyrolysis is the one with the highest adsorption capacity compared to cob and barley husk. This behavior is since the agave material has a more porous structure that favors a larger sur-face area with more active sites. Figure 7-b shows that adsorption is favored mainly in agave activated carbon, followed by the other two materials, which show similar trends in adsorption. This is attributed to the fact that the activation process with phosphoric acid promotes the formation of well-developed mesoporous structures, which translates into larger surfaces and more sites available for adsorption, which is more marked in activated agave carbon given its porous structure and active sites mostly available.

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Figure 7-c shows that activated carbon from barley husk obtained from the microwave-assisted process is the material with the best properties for adsorption, followed by cob and lastly agave. This is due to the effects of microwaves on the inorganic constituents of barley husk on activation with phosphoric acid. Both effects are favorably added, favoring the consolidation of highly developed mesoporous structures with a large number of active sites. In contrast, it is observed that for agave charcoal, the microwave process affects the amount of active sites developed for adsorption since the process favors the formation of mostly basic activated carbons through the elimination of functionalities with acidic oxygen, which are in large quantity in the carbonization of such a precursor, which affects its physical and chemical properties for adsorption.

In a comparative way, it is observed that the pyrolysis process results in materials with megaporous structures that imply fewer active surfaces for adsorption, which is reflected in the decrease in their removal efficiency as the concentration increases (Figure 7-d). On the other hand, the process of chemical activation with phosphoric acid through conventional heating results in materials with well developed mesoporous structures, which translate into larger active surfaces and, therefore, higher removal efficiencies with moderate changes as the concentration of dye increases as seen in Figure 7e. In contrast, Figure 7-f shows that the materials obtained by microwave-assisted activation have larger active surfaces derived from the consolidation of highly developed mesoporous structures with a greater amount of active sites for adsorption. That is why no significant changes are observed in the removal efficiency as the concentration increases.

Figure 7. Effect of the initial concentration on the adsorption capacity and removal efficiency of methylene blue obtained with 0.2 g of adsorbent derived from (a) and (d) pyrolysis, (b) and (e) chemical activation, and (c) and (f) microwave-assisted chemical activation; Initial AM concentration of 10-50 mg/L, particle diameter of 1.5-0.25 mm, pH = 8 and T = 22 °C.

The differences found in removal efficiency are due to the fact that, with a higher concentration of dye, the driving force for mass transfer decreases since the active sites required for adsorption also decrease, which makes the adsorption process methylene blue is slower on the surfaces of activated carbons. That is why at

low concentrations the removal efficiencies in all cases are very close to 90%, since there will be more active sites available on the surface of the adsorbents. These effects are more marked in the materials derived from pyrolysis, followed by those of chemical activation, and are practically insignificant in the materials obtained by microwave-assisted chemical activation. What is observed in the materials of this last process can be justified with what is established by the studies of [23-24] on the adsorption of colorants in activated carbons, who indicate that the mass transfer in highly porous materials increases with concentration, resulting in high adsorption, so they establish that the adsorption of a solute on activated carbons is strongly influenced by the initial concentration of the study solute.

3.11. Kinetic models

3.11.1. Lagergren Models

Figures 8a-c and 8d-f illustrate the pseudo-first order Lagergren models [$\log (q_e - q_t)$ vs. t ; Equation (5)] and pseudo second order [t/q_t vs. t ; Equation (6)], respectively, for the kinetic adsorption processes of the materials obtained by each activation method. Likewise, the values of the parameters of each model are shown in Table 15.

Figure 8. Lagergren kinetic models of [(a), (b) and (c)] Pseudo first order and [(d), (e) and (f)] Pseudo second order for the adsorption of methylene blue with adsorbents obtained from (a) and (d) pyrolysis, (b) and (e) chemical activation and (c) and (f) microwave-assisted chemical activation; particle diameter of 1.5-0.25 mm and $T = 22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Table 15. Constants of the Pseudo first order and Pseudo second order models and correlation coefficients for the adsorption of methylene blue on activated carbons.

Adsorbents		Kinetic Models and Parameters						
		Pseudo first order			Pseudo second order			
Activation method	Activated carbon	K_{ad1} (min^{-1})	q_e (mg/g)	R^2	K_{ad2} (mg/g min)	q_e (mg/g)	h_0 (mg/g min)	R^2
Pyrolysis	Barley	1.0522	34.55	0.9732	0.00087	41.84	1.52	0.9127
	Corn cob	1.0663	23.01	0.9912	0.00161	28.33	1.29	0.9575
	Agave	1.1131	49.19	0.9480	0.00201	84.74	14.43	0.9957
Activation chemistry	Barley	1.0455	77.66	0.9445	0.00015	125.00	23.44	0.8730
	Corn cob	1.0455	81.54	0.9945	0.00038	103.09	4.40	0.9692
MW	Agave	1.0231	82.57	0.9675	0.00019	97.09	1.79	0.8480

According to the literature, the study of adsorption kinetics is of utmost importance since parameters such as adsorption speed (parameter that defines the efficiency of the adsorbent) and the adsorption mechanism can be determined [24]. In this sense, Figure 8-a shows that barley husk pyrolysates ($R^2 = 0.9732$) and cob ($R^2 = 0.9912$) present high correlations and fit the pseudo first order model. In contrast, Figure 8-d shows that the pseudo second order model has very significant correlation coefficient values for agave pyrolyzed ($R^2 = 0.9957$) and, therefore, the process depends on the adsorbent and the adsorbate concentration, and consequently, chemisorption is demonstrated [26].

On the other hand, for carbonaceous materials resulting from the chemical activation process, Figure 8-e illustrates that the correlation coefficients of the pseudo second order kinetic model ($R^2 > 0.98$) are greater than for the pseudo first order kinetic model ($R^2 < 0.95$) in the three materials (Figure 8-b, Table 15). This confirmed that the rate-limiting step is chemisorption, which involves valence forces through the exchange of electrons [24]. In relation to the materials from the microwave-assisted process, Table 15 indicates that the data fit the pseudo first order model (Figure 8-c) with better correlation coefficients ($R^2 > 0.95$) than those obtained for the model of pseudo second order (Figure 8-d).

3.11.2. Weber-Morris model (intraparticle)

The experimental kinetic data q_e versus $t_{0.5}$ were plotted following the Weber-Morris model [Equation (8)] [24, 26]. Figures 9a-c illustrate that some of the graphs do not conform to linearity over the entire contact time range and are observed to occur in three-time intervals. This process was more marked in the adsorption of methylene blue in the pyrolyzed agave (Figure 9-a) and in the three materials that were chemically activated with phosphoric acid (Figure 9-b), which presented a good fit to the model. pseudo-second order confirming that the rate-limiting step is chemisorption [24]. In this sense, it is observed that said graphs are linear in a first stage that occurs within the first 5 minutes and is attributed to the rapid adsorption of cationic methylene blue molecules on the external surface of the materials. Next, a second stage is observed with a gently sloping portion (such as a plateau from 10 to 40 min), which can be attributed to the controlled diffusion of methylene blue in the pores, and very slow since this step presents the smallest K_D values as indicated in Table 16. Finally, a third stage was observed that begins with a moderate diffusion speed in the first internal layers on the subsurface. It can be seen that this third step began at 45 min ($t_{1/2} = 6.70 \text{ min}_{1/2}$) in the indicated materials.

Table 16 shows the kinetic parameters of the Weber-Morris model. The intersection (I) can be interpreted as the starting q_e of each stage described. In this sense, the second stage begins when the surface of the material is saturated with methylene blue molecules (at the value of q_e) and then they begin to diffuse into the pores. Similarly, the third stage begins after the supersaturation of the pores in the next q_e , which is when intraparticle diffusion on the subsurface begins. In relation to this, the second and third processes could explain the high values of q_e calculated by Lagergren's pseudo second order model. Therefore, analysis of the Weber-Morris model reveals rapid external surface adsorption, but also intraparticle diffusion at the subsurface.

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Figure 9. Weber-Morris model for the adsorption of methylene blue with adsorbents obtained from (a) pyrolysis, (b) chemical activation and (c) microwave-assisted chemical activation; particle diameter of 1.5-0.25 mm and T = 22 °C.

Table 16. Constants of the Weber-Morris model and correlation coefficients for the adsorption of methylene blue on activated carbons.

Adsorbent		Stages of the intraparticle diffusion process						
		First	Second			Third		
Activation method	Activated carbon	K_D (mg/g min ^{-0.5})	K_D (mg/g min ^{-0.5})	I (mg/g)	R^2	K_D (mg/g min ^{-0.5})	I (mg/g)	R^2
Pyrolysis	Barley	3.375	3.208	1.156	0.9731	3.473	0.564	0.9953
	Corn cob	2.326	3.228	2.232	0.9919	1.648	7.111	0.9904
	Agave	12.45	13.571	84.74	0.9415	1.118	68.53	0.9703
Activation chemistry	Barley	8.336	4.640	7.669	0.9889	8.297	6.618	0.9812
	Corn cob	11.900	5.671	13.899	0.9908	5.228	25.613	0.9661
MW	Agave	6.309	4.545	3.197	0.9868	7.310	14.598	0.9518

3.11.3. Adsorption isotherms

An adsorption isotherm is the ratio between the amount of substance adsorbed by an adsorbent and the equilibrium pressure or concentration and allows describing the equilibrium of adsorption of a substrate on the active surface of a material at constant temperature. Analyzes of the adsorption processes of the equilibrium experimental data are shown in Figures 10a-c. The results were obtained with the contact times determined in the kinetic experiments, with adsorbent doses of 0.2 g, initial dye concentration of 10-50 mg/L, pH of 8 and constant temperature of 22 °C.

Figure 10. Experimental isotherms of methylene blue adsorption obtained with 0.2 g of adsorbents obtained from (a) pyrolysis, (b) chemical activation and (c) microwave-assisted chemical activation; particle diameter of 1.5-0.25 mm, AM concentration of 10-50 mg / L, pH = 8 and T = 22 °C.

Figure 10-a shows that the pyrolyzed agave is the one with the highest experimental adsorption capacity since it obtained a Q_{exp} of 79.89 mg/g, followed by cob with a Q_{exp} of 67.39 mg/g and finally that of husk. of barley with a Q_{exp} of 52.39 mg/g. These values are due to the fact that agave pyrolyzed has a more porous structure that translates into a larger surface area with more active sites. Figure 10-b shows that adsorption is

mainly favored in agave activated carbon by showing a Q_{exp} of 101.29 mg/g, followed by the other two materials with similar values. Specifically, Q_{exp} of 81.45 mg/g was obtained for activated carbon from barley husk and 80.82 mg/g for activated carbon from cob. These results are attributed to the fact that the activation process with phosphoric acid led to the formation of mesoporous structures that involve larger surfaces and, therefore, more active sites for adsorption, which is mainly observed in agave activated carbon due to its ad that their active sites are mostly available. Figure 10-c shows that activated carbon from barley husk derived from microwave-assisted chemical activation is the material with the best adsorption capacity, followed by cob and lastly agave, with specific Q_{exp} values of 103.01 mg/g, 98.95 mg/g and 95.67 mg/g, respectively. These observed differences were attributed to the effects of microwaves on the activation process and on the constituents of the starting pyrolysates previously exposed, which result in materials with highly developed mesoporous structures and with a large number of active sites, mainly in activated charcoal from barley husk.

3.12. Models of Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms

The equilibrium models were applied to experimental data in the currently linear equations. Figures 10a-c and 10d-f show the linear representations of Langmuir (C_e/q_e vs. C_e) and Freundlich ($\log q_e$ vs. $\log C_e$), respectively, which were applied to the experimental data of adsorption of methylene blue on coals activated. Table 17 shows the parameters calculated for the Langmuir and Freundlich models. It is observed that the Langmuir linear model fits the experimental data obtained with the materials obtained by pyrolysis with values of $R^2 = 0.99$, which are very significant. These results suggest that methylene blue adsorption takes place at specific and homogeneous sites in a monolayer.

Langmuir's maximum adsorption capacity values were calculated by Equation (9); the Q_{max} values showed certain differences compared to the experimental Q_{exp} values obtained with the carbons chemically activated in a conventional and micro-wave-assisted manner. Therefore, adsorption might not be solely surface related, and another phenomenon might be present such as multilayer formation, as predicted by Freundlich's model. Likewise, the Langmuir constants were low for the materials derived from the microwave process showing values of $K_L = 0.093$ for activated carbon from barley husk, $K_L = 0.098$ for activated carbon from cob, and $K_L = 0.086$ for activated carbon from agave, suggesting a low-energy interaction between methylene blue and the surface of these materials [26].

Freundlich's model describes adsorption as non-ideal and multilayer [43] (Foo and Hameed, 2010). The results obtained with the chemically activated carbons in its two variants showed a good fit to Freundlich's linear model since they presented high correlations with R^2 values > 0.98 , mainly in the materials obtained by conventional chemical activation ($R^2 = 0.99$).

In addition to the above, the exponential coefficient ($1/n$) is related to the extension of the adsorbent heterogeneity, which is higher as $1/n$ is closer to 0. The adsorption systems with the pyrolysis materials presented values $1/n$ between 0.45 and 0.68, between 0.26 and 0.44 for chemically activated carbons, and between 0.72 and 0.75 for activated carbons with the microwave assisted process.

These results suggest that the adsorption capacities of chemically activated carbons might not be related only to the surface and, therefore, the phenomenon pertinent to the formation of multilayers would take place, as predicted by the Freundlich model. Table 17 shows that the chemically activated materials presented the lowest $1/n$ value (followed by those obtained by pyrolysis and lastly those obtained by the microwave-assisted process); consequently, they have the greatest heterogeneity. This heterogeneity agrees with the results of the Weber-Morris kinetic model for materials derived from chemical activation, showing consecutive stages of adsorption on the external surface, pores, and diffusion.

Table 17. Constants of the Langmuir and Freundlich models and correlation coefficients for the adsorption of methylene blue on activated carbons.

Adsorbents		Isotherm and Parameters							
		Langmuir				Freundlich			
Método de activación	Activated coal	K_L (L/mg)	Q_{max} (mg/g)	R_L	R^2	K_F (L/mg)	n	1/n	R^2
Pyrolysis	Barley	0.6679	55.25	0.03-0.13	0.9994	23.9773	3.76	0.26	0.8789
	Corn cob	0.5195	74.07	0.04-0.16	0.9971	26.3208	2.84	0.35	0.8489
	Agave	0.3262	93.46	0.06-0.23	0.9994	25.3921	2.27	0.44	0.9344
Activation chemistry	Barley	0.0937	222.22	0.17-0.52	0.9777	20.4033	1.33	0.75	0.9941
	Corn cob	0.0988	200.00	0.17-0.05	0.9606	19.4491	1.36	0.73	0.9857
MW	Agave	0.0862	188.68	0.19-0.54	0.9746	16.7147	1.37	0.72	0.9827

4. Conclusions

The optimal and reproducible conditions for microwave-assisted chemical activation were 200 W (level 1), 4 min (level 2), 60% H_3PO_4 (level 2), and 200 cm^3N_2/min (level 3). Under these conditions activated carbons were obtained with yields of 72% for agave, 96% for cob and 93% for barley, with % C of 61-68%. The materials obtained through this process presented greater active surfaces derived from the consolidation of highly developed mesoporous structures with a greater number of active sites for adsorption derived from the effects of the activation agent and microwaves, which translated into removal efficiencies and capacities. significant adsorption rates as the dye concentration increased.

The differences in the times for the adsorption of methylene blue during the kinetic studies were attributed to the porous structure developed in each activation process and to the availability and quantity of active sites present in the materials.

The kinetic and equilibrium studies showed that the pseudo-first order model presented the best fit for adsorption on carbons obtained by pyrolysis and micro-wave-assisted chemical activation. In contrast, the pseudo-second order model presented the best fit for adsorption processes on materials obtained by chemical activation, suggesting that chemisorption is the limiting step that determines the speed of the adsorption process.

The Weber-Morris intraparticle diffusion model described three stages represented by the rapid formation of an adsorbate layer on the external surface, gradual adsorption in which intraparticle diffusion is the limiting factor that controls the rate, and by moderate intraparticle diffusion on the subsurface. These different regions of adsorption rate were indicative of rapid external surface adsorption and intraparticle diffusion at the subsurface.

The equilibrium data showed that the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm models were adequate to describe the adsorption of methylene blue in the materials obtained, which confirms that the adsorption of dye was heterogeneous and occurred through physicochemical interactions. The equilibrium data showed that the Langmuir isotherm is adequate to describe the adsorption processes on the carbons obtained by pyrolysis ($R^2 > 0.90$), which suggests that the adsorption of methylene blue takes place at specific and homogeneous sites in a monolayer. The Freundlich isotherm was suitable for the adsorption processes on coals obtained by chemical activation in its two variants since they presented high correlations ($R^2 > 0.98$). This confirmed that the adsorption of methylene blue could not only be related to the surface, but that the adsorption in multilayers could be present on a heterogeneous surface as predicted by this model. Such heterogeneity was consistent with the results of the Weber-Morris kinetic model showing consecutive adsorption stages on the outer surface, pores, and diffusion.

The high adsorption capacities obtained with the carbons derived from the microwave-assisted activation process made it possible to demonstrate that microwave radiation has numerous advantages over conventional methods since it produces specific effects on the surface chemistry of the carbonaceous material prepared by increasing the C/O ratio. Or and decrease functional groups that contain acidic

oxygen, which resulted in mostly basic activated carbons that were highly effective in adsorption processes of methylene blue.

The results obtained allow to establish that barley husk, corn cobs and *Agave salmiana* leaves are potential precursors for obtaining novel carbonaceous materials that allow building the basis of a line of research focused on the viable and environmentally responsible use of lignocellulosic residues to obtain materials with greater added value and potential application in adsorption processes of positively charged molecules or ions.

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